

An Efficient Spam Email Filtering Approach Using Machine Learning

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Abstract— Email is among the most extensively used communication techniques. Fraud Emails or Spam Emails has become a major concern as it is valueless to the recipient. It is a wastage of network capacity and filtering spam emails are time consuming and removing all of these is a concerning issue. There are various methods to categorize emails, such as Naïve Bayes, SVM etc. This Paper proposes a system to predict spam mails using machine learning in Google Colab a Jupyter notebook environment.

Keywords — Email Classification, Spam Filtering, Email classification

I. INTRODUCTION:

Email has become a part of everyday life as the most popular mode of communication. Spam, often known as unwanted, junk, or unsolicited email, is one of the most significant issues with email usage. According to Spam laws, approximately 85% of all emails are spam, with advertisements, adult-related, and unwelcome emails accounting for 36 percent, 31.7 percent, and 26.5 percent of the content, accordingly. Email filtering is the process of sorting email based on a set of criteria. Logistic Regression and Naïve Bayes Classification algorithms are the well-known classification algorithm among the different approaches for email filtering.

II. DESCRIPTION

When it comes to email, the term "spam" refers to "unsolicited bulk email." The term "unsolicited" refers to a message that has been sent without the recipient's explicit authorization. Bulk messaging refers to sending a message as part of a larger group of messages with substantially identical content. Only when a message is both unsolicited and bulk is it considered spam.

Unsolicited Email is just email like first contact enquiries, job enquiries and sales enquiries, whereas bulk email is the same as regular email such as subscriber newsletter, customer communications and discussion lists.

Spam filters capture unwanted, inappropriate, and virus-infested email (also known as spam) and prevent it from reaching inboxes. Spam filters are used by Internet Service Providers (ISPs) to ensure that they are not transmitting

spam. Spam filters are also used by small and medium-sized organizations (SMBs) to protect their employees and networks.

Spam Filtering Method Using Rules is performed here. Algorithms provide a score to the messages in e-mails based on pre-defined rules in the form of a regular expression. They categorize emails into spam and non-spam groups based on the ratings they earn.

Key facts

- According to experts, a malicious computer virus or worm known as "Stration" is to blame for the increase in spam. This takes over personal computers and forces them to send e-mails.
- Share tipping e-mail scams that is "pump and dump" are becoming more common. Fraudsters buy low-cost, obscure stocks and then promote them by e-mail. When others invest in a company, its stock price rises. The fraudsters then profitably sell their stake, causing the price to plummet.
- Phishing scam e-mails, which solicit recipients to enter their bank details on Web sites that appear like those of legitimate institutions, are also on the rise. Of course, the websites are fake.
- Experts advise computer users to install and update anti-virus software, never react to spam e-mails, and never give financial information. [1]

Data mining

Data mining is a technical approach that analyses large amounts of dispersed data in order to make meaning of it and convert it into knowledge. To forecast outcomes, it searches millions of records for deviations, trends, or associations.

Data mining has a variety of applications, including:

To remove noise and repeats from data, retrieve relevant data and then use it to analyze potential outcomes, make more informed and timely business decisions.

For extracting models characterizing significant classes or predicting future data trends, there are two types of data analysis that can be applied. The following are the two forms classification and prediction. Prediction models are used to predict continuous valued function

Data cleansing, artificial intelligence (AI), association rule learning, clustering, classification, data analytics, data warehousing, machine learning, and regression are some of the most commonly utilized functionalities.

III. PURPOSE OF THE STUDY

This article aims to classify and find spam emails by examining various data sets and utilizing mining algorithms that is logistic regression and linear regression to classify spam email from ham mails. The dataset used in this study has 2 categories that is spam and ham and 2 fields that is category and message. We are using this data set to train a dataset and find out the accurate algorithm and its accuracy and design a suitable model for testing". The accuracy is compared to know which algorithm comes up with best accuracy value.

IV. METHODOLOGY

This paper is all about the analyzing the spam mails and classifying the dataset to spam and ham by help of an algorithm and the Google Colab platform. The platform used here is Colaboratory, which is a product from Google Research

Google Colab

Google Research's Colaboratory, or "Colab" by brief, is a web-based Python editor that allows anyone to write and run random Python code. It's notably useful for machine learning, data analysis, and education. Colab is a hosted Jupyter notebook service that doesn't require any setup and offers free access to computational resources, notably GPUs.

Google Colab is a cloud-based alternative of the Jupyter notebook environment that is completely free. The most essential aspect of Google collab is that it doesn't require any setup, and the notes you generate may be changed by your members of the team in real time, much like Google Docs pages. Many common machine learning libraries are supported by Colab and can be quickly loaded into your notebook. [3]

Properties of colab

- Python allows you to write and run code.
- Record the code that underpins the mathematical formulae.
- Make some new notebooks.
- Existing notebooks can be uploaded.
- Use the google link to share the notebooks.
- Content from Google Drive can be imported.
- Google Drive notebooks can be saved to/from.

- External datasets, such as those from Kaggle, can be imported.
- PyTorch, TensorFlow, Keras, and OpenCV can all be used together.
- A free cloud service with a free GPU and TPU is available.

V. IMPLEMENTATION

Here logistic regression is applied on a given data set in order to create model to find fraud email from a set of emails.

The logistic regression model calculates the likelihood of each result. It gives us the probability that $y=1$, i.e., the likelihood that an email is spam. To do classification, we can compare this likelihood to a threshold.

Data source

Here we consider the dataset from Kaggle repository[5], which contains 2 categories that is spam and ham and 2 fields that is category and message.

The data set from Kaggle repository contains the attributes of category and some emails such that both spam and ham are present. This data set is used as training data for the classifier. [4]

Figure 1: Attributes and its values

- Notebooks from GitHub can be imported and published.

	Category	Message
0	ham	Go until jurong point, crazy.. Available only ...
1	ham	Ok lar... Joking wif u oni...
2	spam	Free entry in 2 a wkly comp to win FA Cup fina...
3	ham	U dun say so early hor... U c already then say...
4	ham	Nah I don't think he goes to usf, he lives aro...
...	...	...
5567	spam	This is the 2nd time we have tried 2 contact u...
5568	ham	Will ü b going to esplanade fr home?
5569	ham	Pity, * was in mood for that. So...any other s...
5570	ham	The guy did some bitching but I acted like i'd...
5571	ham	Rofl. Its true to its name

[5572 rows x 2 columns]

	Category	Message
0	ham	Go until jurong point, crazy.. Available only ...
1	ham	Ok lar... Joking wif u oni...
2	spam	Free entry in 2 a wkly comp to win FA Cup fina...
3	ham	U dun say so early hor... U c already then say...
4	ham	Nah I don't think he goes to usf, he lives aro...

Algorithms

Logistic Regression: It's a classification algorithm, not a regression one. It's used to estimate discrete values (like 0/1, yes/no, and true/false) based on a set of independent variables. In simple terms, it fits data to a logit function to forecast the probability of an event occurring.[4] As a result, it's also called logit regression. Its output values are between 0 and 1 because it forecasts probability.

```
#encode labels(converts spam and ham to 0 & 1)
mail_data.loc[mail_data['Category'] == 'spam', 'Category',] = 0
mail_data.loc[mail_data['Category'] == 'ham', 'Category',] = 1
```

```
# separating the data as texts and label
X = mail_data['Message']
Y = mail_data['Category']
```

Figure2: Encode and separate data

The workflow is first the imported dataset is processed that is the data is converted to numbers. Then the dataset is split into training and testing dataset. This will be given to the logistic regression model, which creates a trained logistic regression model. Finally give a mail to this model to classify normal emails and spam.[5]

Numpy, pandas, accuracy, logistic regression and idfvectorizer are the libraries or function that is imported. Replace all the missing values or null values by str. The labels that is spam and ham is encoded as 0 and 1 respectively.[6] Then the data is split into features and targets.

Then forms training and testing dataset. Then the generated model is evaluated using the training dataset. After this the accuracy rate is found. If there is huge difference between the accuracy of training data and testing data it could cause overfitting. An array is created to store the data as a list. The dataset is then given to predictive model.[7][8]

```
print(X.shape)
print(X_train.shape)
print(X_test.shape)

(5572,)
(4457,)
(1115,)

[ ] #Feature Extraction
# transform the text data to feature vectors that can be used as input to the Logistic regression
feature_extraction = TfidfVectorizer(min_df = 1, stop_words='english', lowercase='True')

X_train_features = feature_extraction.fit_transform(X_train)
X_test_features = feature_extraction.transform(X_test)

# convert Y_train and Y_test values as integers
Y_train = Y_train.astype('int')
Y_test = Y_test.astype('int')
```

Figure3: Divide the data to train & test data.

model is trained, it is then evaluated using the test dataset. Then the accuracy obtained by the training dataset and the test dataset is evaluated, to come to the correct conclusion.

```
[ ] input_mail = ["Is that seriously how you spell his name?"]

# convert text to feature vectors
input_data_features = feature_extraction.transform(input_mail)

# making prediction

prediction = model.predict(input_data_features)
print(prediction)

if (prediction[0]==1):
    print('Ham mail')
else:
    print('Spam mail')

[1]
Ham mail
```

Figure3: Summary for model using Logistic Regression

We see that the accuracy received by the training set with the logistic regression model is equal to 96%.

VI. CONCLUSION

For binary and linear classification problems, logistic regression is a simple and more efficient method. It's a classification model that's simple to implement and delivers excellent results with linearly separable classes.[9] In the industrial world, it is a widely used categorization method.

Logistic Regression is a machine learning approach that predicts the outcome using known parameters that are connected with the output. The known parameters are utilized to create a consistent and continuous slope that is used to anticipate the unknown or result. Here, there is not much difference in the accuracy value achieved from the training data set and test data, that is they are similar and thus no overfitting is found.

VII. REFERENCES

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The model is then trained by the training dataset. After the

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